

DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY PLATFORM OF SMART CITIES

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Abstract: *A smart city can be defined as an urban area that uses sensors for electronic data collection located in infrastructure, buildings, vehicles, institutions and devices (Internet of Things) to provide information in real time for the purpose of functioning of operating systems in the city. These operating systems include energy, transportation, water supply, sanitation, waste, law enforcement, information and communication. The backbone of smart cities consists of two technologies: IoT technology and big data technology. These technologies, in fact, make up the information technology platform of smart cities that we analyze in this paper.*

Keywords: *Information technology platform, smart cities, big data technology, Internet of Things.*

1. Introduction

The use of information and communication technologies in cities for various city activities has led to increased efficiency in city operations and these cities have been labeled with terms such as digital cities and smart cities. A smart city is the effective integration of physical and digital systems, as well as human resources into the built environment, to ensure a sustainable, prosperous and inclusive future for citizens (Yin et al. 2015).

The components of a smart city include smart infrastructure, smart transportation, smart energy, smart healthcare and smart technology. These components are what make cities smart and efficient, while information and communication technologies enable the

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transformation of traditional cities into smart cities. A special role in this transformation is played by IoT technology and big data technology, which forms the information technology (IT) platform of smart cities. We will see how these technologies participate in the development of the IT platform of smart cities after considering the characteristics of smart cities.

2. Characteristics of smart cities

A smart city is an urban area whose functioning depends to a large extent on an IT platform that provides basic infrastructure for a decent quality of life for its citizens, a clean and sustainable environment and the application of smart application solutions in many areas, such as: adequate water supply, safe electricity supply, solid waste management, efficient urban mobility and public transport, affordable housing, comprehensive information technology connectivity and digitalization, good e-governance and citizen participation, sustainable environment, security of citizens, health and education (Batty et al. 2012).

In a smart city environment, city officials can also encourage participatory governance, improve cooperation between different economic actors, encourage innovative business models in the private and public sectors and, ultimately, promote urban sustainable development, more competitive business and a creative environment (Silva, Khan, Han, 2018).

To meet the needs of citizens, city officials and urban planners should focus on building the entire urban eco-system, which represents the four pillars of comprehensive and sustainable development: institutional, physical, social and economic infrastructure. This can be a long-term goal and cities can work to gradually develop such a comprehensive infrastructure, adding layers and increasing the degree of intelligence of cities over a longer period of time.

The degree of transformation of traditional cities and the development of smart cities varies from city to city and from country to country, depending on the level of economic development, readiness for changes and reforms, resources and aspirations of city residents. The six most common characteristics of smart cities are: smart economy, smart people, smart governance, smart mobility, smart environment and smart urban life.

The smart economy is about efficiency in the use of energy; innovations in the production and service sector, economic impact on the quality of life of citizens, return on investment and circular economy (Harrison, Donnelly, 2011). Smart people mean connected citizens, employees and city visitors who can use e-health and e-learning services. Smart government refers to the digital automation of e-government processes, open data and citizen participation (Ahvenniemi et al. 2017). Smart mobility means urban planning, the development of intelligent transport systems and intelligent parking solutions as well as traffic and mobility management (Letaifa, 2015). Smart environment refers to water and waste management, energy management, monitoring of environmental indicators, sustainable processes and urbanization, as well as hybrid approaches to production. Smart urban living includes cultural facilities, e-health, social services and public safety, such as surveillance systems and emergency service networks.

3. IoT and sensor technology as a component of the IT platform of smart cities

Smart cities must have three key features: intelligence, interconnection and instrumentation that the Internet of Things can provide (Mikalef et al. 2018). The use of smart phones, smart meters, smart sensors and radio frequency identification (RFID) essentially make up the IoT framework in smart cities. The Internet of Things is a network of interconnected physical objects (called "things") including computers, smartphones, sensors, actuators, wearables, homes, buildings, structures, vehicles, and energy systems. The Internet of Things enables the communication of many different types of systems and applications to provide increasingly smarter, more reliable and safer services. A large number of sensors connect buildings, infrastructure, transport, networks and utilities through IT. Various tasks such as information exchange and communication, intelligent recognition, location determination, monitoring, pollution control and identity management can be performed using IoT technology.

Generally speaking, IoT refers to the technology through which many objects (people, animals, things) with embedded microprocessors are connected, mostly wirelessly, to the Internet. Embedding mobile devices everywhere in various objects and connecting all devices to the Internet enables broad communication between users and objects. This type of interaction opens the door to many applications (Ahvenniemi et al. 2017).

Figure 1: The working process of IoT technology

Source: Mikalef et al. 2018.

The working process of IoT technology is explained in Figure 1. The Internet ecosystem (at the top of the figure) includes a large number of things. Sensors and other devices collect information from the ecosystem. This information can be stored and/or

processed using various tools, including data mining tools. This analysis turns information into knowledge and/or intelligence. Machine learning can help turn knowledge into decision support (made by humans and/or machines). Decisions help create innovative applications, new business models and improve business processes. Most existing applications are in the upper part of the picture, which means that sensors help create knowledge. However, now the focus is shifting to the whole cycle, i.e. sensors help both in creating knowledge and in taking actions.

In essence, the Internet of Things can be said to be a network of physical objects-devices, vehicles, buildings and other entities with embedded electronics, software, sensors and network connectivity that enable these objects to collect and exchange data. The Internet of Things allows objects to be sensed and controlled remotely through existing network infrastructure, creating opportunities for more direct integration of the physical world into computer-based systems and resulting in improved efficiency, accuracy and economic benefits. When the IoT is augmented with sensors and actuators, this technology becomes an example of a general class of cyber-physical systems that includes smart grids, smart homes, intelligent transportation, and smart cities. Each thing is uniquely recognizable through its embedded computer system (microprocessor), but is able to interoperate and interact within the existing Internet infrastructure. Therefore, IoT is a connected ecosystem that has the following features: a large number of objects (things) can be connected, each thing has a unique identifier (IP address), objects have the ability to receive, send and store data (and do that automatically), data is delivered via wireless Internet and is built on Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communication.

4. Big data technology as a component of the IT platform of smart cities

Big data technology is another important component of the IT platform of smart cities. The definition of big data incorporates multiple dimensions. In this context, this technology refers to a larger volume of information, but also to new types of data, as well as new types of data analysis together with real-time information and non-traditional forms of data from different media. Undoubtedly, this is a new data-driven technology that deals with the analytics of large volumes of data, including social media data. The focus of this technology is on three main categories: the data itself, the analysis of that data, and the presentation of the results of the analyzes that enable the creation of new values.

The term big data analytics is used to emphasize the processes and tools used to gain insight and obtain useful information from large amounts of data. The information technologies used in big data analysis are various analytical platforms and tools, the most important being Apache Hadoop and ApacheSpark. The former is an open-source framework for distributed processing and storage of big data, while ApacheSpark is a popular open-source data processing and analysis platform suitable for performing various machine learning tasks (Gupta, George, 2016).

A special category of big data relevant for smart cities is mobile big data. The primary source of mobile big data is the huge number of smart phones, which are connected to cellular mobile networks and generate massive amounts of data. Other sources are IoT, mobile social networks, wireless sensor networks as well as wearable wireless devices and wireless vehicle networks. All these components make up the typical architecture of modern mobile networks. Urban environments where mobile devices are portable and have

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a large number of mobile users indicate that mobile big data analytics are more demanding than standard big data analytics (Cheng et al. 2017).

Data from mobile devices can contain useful information needed for problem solving such as fraud detection, targeted and marketing advertising campaigns, and data that can be used to improve healthcare. In addition, the data can be used to improve traffic management, to improve location-based and context-aware services, or to improve general security. The unique value of data from mobile devices is precisely its ubiquity and contextual sensitivity. Mobile big data analytics is precisely about discovering previously unknown and potentially meaningful information, patterns, and connections among data collected by mobile device users, either at the mobile network level or at the application level.

Here we should also mention the resources that cities must have in order to transform big data into useful information, decisions and actions to improve the lives and work of people in cities. The transformation of cities from traditional to smart cities, which is data-driven, is an extremely complex process and requires a high level of management (Aker, Wamba, 2016). That is why there should be capacities that actually define a city's ability to use big data, in order to gain strategic or operational benefits, that is, to make informed decisions that can provide additional benefits to the residents of that city. Therefore, these capacities are defined as the city's ability to collect, integrate and develop its own big data resources. The main resources that are distinguished are divided into three categories: 1. infrastructural resources in terms of information systems and data, 2. other non-structural resources in terms of certain norms, regulations, laws and urban culture itself and 3. human resources, in terms of skills and knowledge of the city administration, both in the field of data analytics and management capabilities (Saritas et al.2021).

5. The role of the IT platform in the development and functioning of smart cities

The IT platform of smart cities or urban computing has four roles: implementation of sensor and IoT technology in the urban environment (urban sensing), data management, data analytics and delivery of services (Figure 2) (Alshuwaikhat, Aina, Binsaedan, 2022).

Urban sensing. As previously mentioned, using the Internet of Things (IoT) and sensor technology, cities are generating massive amounts of data. In cities, there are many parameters that need to be measured and monitored by sensors, such as air pollution, weather conditions, traffic density and quality of roads, water and electricity supply, etc. For these reasons, the implementation of IoT and sensor technology in urban areas enables the development of advanced analytical solutions for managers and decision makers in city management structures. Sensors and IoT devices are more efficient if they are networked and have the computing capacity to provide meaningful information from the collected data, thereby promoting environmental sustainability (Kontokosta, 2021).

Data management. In smart cities, data is generated from different sources and may have different levels of sensitivity (privacy and security issues) and quality. Data from social networks and data on mobility, movement of people are organized by an indexing structure that integrates spatiotemporal and textual information for efficient analysis. Because there are security issues associated with data, data management depends on the sensitivity of the data. Data can be managed more efficiently and effectively if it is properly

categorized by level of sensitivity. In addition, in order to protect data privacy, it is proposed to divide data into three categories: sensitive, quasi-sensitive and open data (Liu et al., 2021). Based on sensitive data, a person can be directly identified, as can, for example, based on a social security number. Quasi-sensitive data can be used to identify a person when linked to other sources such as social media, which include age, gender, address, etc. Finally, open data is freely available to the public and can be accessed quickly. Different strategies are used to manage the sharing and dissemination of data based on its sensitivity and classification.

Figure 2: IT platform of smart cities

Source: Alshuwaikhat, Aina, Binsaedan, 2022.

Data analysis. As we have already emphasized, IoT devices connected to collect urban data over the Internet generate a huge amount of data. The integration of all smart systems (smart homes, smart parking, etc.) and IoT devices (sensors, actuators and smartphones) is desirable for more efficient data collection and analysis. Big data technology is a very useful tool for processing and analyzing data from numerous sources (e.g. real-time sensors, remote sensing, online streaming, social web networks, e-health, etc.) and with different structures and types (e.g. IoT, machine-to-machine communication, databases, Internet communication, wireless sensor networks, etc.). Big data is defined by three basic characteristics – high volume, high speed of generation and high variety. These features help in the analysis of city data and the results can be effectively used for digital transformation and smart city management (Hassan et al., 2021).

Delivery of services. The last role of the smart city IT platform is to provide services and it is realized by creating smart city services and solutions based on data analysis and the information obtained. This information is integrated into higher-level services or applications, which improves the quality of smart city services. The latest

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advances in artificial intelligence contribute to the examination of ways to use artificial intelligence devices in service delivery (Shi and Zhang, 2021).

The smart city IT platform with its applications and tools helps city decision makers to collect, analyze and interpret data and derive useful knowledge to alleviate urban problems and provide services to meet urban policy goals. In this way, the city administration can significantly increase the efficiency of decision-making in solving urban problems, such as: pollution, traffic congestion, disaster mitigation, maintenance of large infrastructure facilities and housing. The ultimate goal of this kind of efficient urban management is to provide the residents of the city with an unhindered performance of daily activities and a better quality of life.

6. Conclusion

The Internet of Things, sensor technology and big data are basic technologies for the development of smart cities. It can be said that there are no smart cities without the application of these technologies that form an IT platform for the development of smart solutions related to the functioning of modern cities. The spatially and temporally tagged urban data generated in smart cities are actually huge amounts of data that need to be processed and analyzed using analytical tools. From the analysis of these data, useful information and knowledge can be obtained for the smart management of all services that a city can provide to residents in their private, social and business life. Therefore, all data from IoT systems and other elements of mobile computing are integrated into information and communication technology platforms, in order to enable city managers and decision makers to optimize the efficiency and effectiveness of city operations and services by connecting and managing those systems remotely, but also by connecting and communicating with interested parties (citizens, businesses, institutions and citizen organizations).

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RAZVOJ INFORMACIONO-TEHNOLOŠKE PLATFORME PAMETNIH GRADOVA

Rezime: Pametan grad se može definisati kao urbano područje koje koristi senzore za elektronsko prikupljanje podataka koji se nalaze u infrastrukturi, zgradama, vozilima, institucijama i uređajima (Internet stvari) za pružanje informacija u realnom vremenu u svrhu funkcionisanja operativnih sistema u gradu. Ovi operativni sistemi uključuju energiju, transport, vodosnabdevanje, kanalizaciju, otpad, sprovođenje zakona, informisanje i komunikaciju. Okosnicu pametnih gradova čine dve tehnologije: IoT tehnologija i tehnologija velikih podataka. Ove tehnologije, u stvari, čine informaciono-tehnološku platformu pametnih gradova koju analiziramo u ovom radu.

Ključne reči: Informaciono-tehnološka platforma, pametni gradovi, tehnologija velikih podataka, Internet stvari.